

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Deployment of three pairs of Argo floats

Milestone MS1

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Milestone report

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Cover sheet: One float profiler in the water in front of the Ross ice shelf. Credits: Craig Stewart, NIWA)

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1. Means of verification of the achievement of the milestone

A total of 8 ARGO float profilers were deployed between December 2023 and March 2024.

2. Work performed and main achievements

In collaboration with Korean, New Zealand and Italian colleagues, 4 ARGO float profilers were deployed by **UKRI-BAS** in the Amundsen and Ross Sea, in the Western sector of Antarctic shelf seas. Their trajectories and the data they accrued to date are available on the numerous ARGO databases, e.g. at the following links:

<https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/1902687>

<https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/5907093>

<https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/4903786>

<https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/3902582>

In addition, **AWI** deployed 4 ARGO float profilers in the Eastern sector of Antarctic Shelf seas, next to the Amery ice shelf, and in collaboration with Australian colleagues who used the same AWI campaigns to deploy profilers closer to the Denman ice shelf, broadening the spatial coverage. These 4 profilers bring the total of deployments made by OCEAN:ICE to 8, instead of the promised three pairs (i.e. instead of 6 profilers). These floats use the Global Positioning System (GPS) to establish their positions and use Iridium to transmit their data. Trajectories and data from the latter batch of profilers is also available on all ARGO databases, notably here:

<https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/6990622>

<https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/4903780>

<https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/5907087>

<https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/6990621>

Two additional profilers are planned for deployment in austral Summer 2024-25, in front of Totten ice shelf, in collaboration with Japanese collaborators. OCEAN:ICE efforts demonstrated the capability of profilers to provide exciting observations in data deserts. Whilst most profilers remain under sea-ice at the time this report is written, one profiler was able to reach the ocean surface in the Amundsen Sea over the austral winter season, as the polynya there remained open, somewhat surprisingly (a fact that we are investigating thanks to these unique profiler observations, among others).

This success collaborated to starting a trend, with numerous colleagues and programmes now forecasted to deploy profilers in various sectors of Antarctic shelf seas.